

THE IMPORTANCE OF METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

This article provides information about the importance of different methods and their types in teaching foreign languages. In addition, in this article I will give a brief description of each method.

Key words: method, teaching, learning, different, using, improve, listening, reading, speaking, effectively, quickly, easily, language, memorize, approach, education, teachers, students, grammar

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Firstly, I will give some information about method and methodology in the following paragraph. Methodology refers to the overarching strategy and rationale of your research project. It involves studying the methods used in your field and the theories or principles behind them, in order to develop an approach that matches your objectives.

There are various methods of teaching foreign languages similar to the Audio-Lingual method, Grammar-Translation method, The Direct method, Total Physical Response, Communicative Language Teaching, Task-based language learning, the Natural Approach and the Structural Approach.

- The Direct Method

In this method, the teaching is done entirely in the language being learned. The learner is not allowed to use his or her original language. Grammar rules are avoided and there is an emphasis on good pronunciation.

- Grammar-Translation

In this method, learning is largely by translation to and from the target language. Grammar rules are to be memorized and long lists of vocabulary learned by heart. There is little or no emphasis placed on developing oral ability. This method is most commonly used in secondary education.

- Audio-Lingual

The theory behind this method is that learning a language means acquiring habits. There is much practice of dialogues in every situation. New language is first heard and extensively drilled before being seen in its written form.

- The Structural Approach

This method sees language as a complex of grammatical rules which are to be learned one at a time in a set order. So, for example the verb “to be” is introduced and practiced before the present continuous tense which uses “to be” as an auxiliary. This method of learning is common in language learning apps.

- Total Physical Response (TPR)

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TPR works by having the learner respond to simple commands such as “Stand up”, “Close your book”, “Go to the window and open it.” The method stresses the importance of aural comprehension and the importance of kinesthetic learning.

- Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)

The focus of this method is to enable the learner to communicate effectively and appropriately in the various situations she would be likely to find herself in. The content of CLT courses are functions such as inviting, suggesting, complaining, or notions such as the expression of time, quantity, location. Much like The Structural Approach, this method is commonly used in language learning apps.

- Task-based language learning

The focus of the teaching is on the completion of a task which in itself is interesting to the learners. Learners use the language they already have to complete the task and there is little correction of errors. The aim here is to highlight the importance of learning the language by making it vital to task completion

- The Natural Approach

This approach, propounded by Professor S. Krashen, stresses the similarities between learning the first and second languages. There is no correction of mistakes. Learning takes place by the students being exposed to language that is comprehensible or made comprehensible to them.

The methods mentioned above will greatly help us in teaching and learning a second language. In addition, we can further develop education through these methods. I believe that we can learn and teach foreign languages faster, easier and more effectively using these methods. In addition, these methods create various conveniences for teachers and students in learning and teaching a second language I hope that everyone will achieve their goals if they learn foreign languages using this method they like.

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